

GPM2220000320: peptide model: 7400.1.1 of ENSMUSP0000064155

ENSMUSP0000064155: Rif1.p, no protein text annotation available

Sample information

log(e) log(I) m+h delta ζ sequence
 7400 -10.1 4.14 1555.5673 -0.0015 2/2 srrr¹⁴¹⁴SEAVDS^CSD^SQER¹⁴²⁶esgq (1261) 0.01
 mods: C1420+Carbamidomethyl, S1423+Phospho, R1426+Label:+6 Da

controllerType=0 controllerNumber=1 scan=7401

S E ¹A ^{IV}D ^SI ^SC ^SI ^DS ^QE R

matched/total: # ions: 80% intensity: 93% μ: -0.03, σ: 0.04 Da

bond	+1 _y	+1 _y -17	+1 _y -18	+1 _b	+1 _b -17	+1 _b -18
S ₁	1468.535	1451.509	1450.525	88.039	71.013	70.029
E ₂	1339.493	1322.466	1321.482	217.082	200.055	199.071
A ₃	1268.456	1251.429	1250.445	288.119	271.092	270.108
V ₄	1169.387	1152.361	1151.377	387.187	370.161	369.177
D ₅	1054.360	1037.334	1036.350	502.214	485.188	484.204
S ₆	967.328	950.302	949.318	589.246	572.220	571.236
C ₇	807.298	790.271	789.287	749.277	732.251	731.266
S ₈	720.266	703.239	702.255	836.309	819.283	818.299
D ₉	605.239	588.212	587.228	951.336	934.309	933.325
S ₁₀	438.240	421.214	420.230	1118.334	1101.308	1100.324
Q ₁₁	310.182	293.155	292.171	1246.393	1229.366	1228.382
E ₁₂	181.139	164.113	163.129	1375.436	1358.409	1357.425

Other observed ions:

ion type	m/z	ion type	m/z
by[3-5]	286.140	a[4]	359.187
ay[2-5]	387.187	by[2-6]	502.214
ay[7-10]	502.100	y[10]-H ₃ PO ₄ ⁺²	585.731
ay[6-10]	589.132	y[11]-H ₃ PO ₄ ⁺²	621.250
y[5]-H ₃ PO ₄	622.266	by[4-9]	664.224
y[6]-H ₃ PO ₄	709.298	y[13]-H ₃ PO ₄ ⁺²	729.287
by[2-8]	749.277	(parent-2H ₂ O) ⁺²	760.277
(parent-H ₃ PO ₄) ²	766.272	(parent-H ₂ O) ⁺²	769.282
ay[2-9]	836.309	y[7]-H ₃ PO ₄	869.328
y[8]-H ₃ PO ₄	956.360	by[6-13]	1036.350
y[9]-H ₃ PO ₄	1071.387	b[11]-H ₃ PO ₄	1148.393
by[5-13]	1151.377	y[11]-H ₃ PO ₄	1241.493

Residue modification sets tested:

- Complete mods:** i. Carbamidomethyl@C, Label:+6 Da@R, Label:+6 Da@K
- Potential mods:** i. Phospho@S, Phospho@T, Phospho@Y
 ii. Oxidation@M, Oxidation@W, Deamidated@N, Deamidated@Q
 iii. Dioxidation@M, Dioxidation@W
- Protein-specific PTMs:** i. Phospho@S, Acetyl@K
- N-terminal:** i. Ammonia-loss@Q, Ammonia-loss@C, Dehydrated@E (peptide)
 ii. ragged, Acetyl (protein)

E-value calculation:

